

THE USEFULNESS OF DERMOSCOPY FOR THE RECOGNITION OF MALIGNANT COLLISION TUMORS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Preoperative diagnosis of malignant collision tumors (MCT) is extremely difficult. The value of dermoscopy to improve the correct detection of these tumors has not been previously studied.

Objective: To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of MCT with and without dermoscopy and to describe the dermoscopic features of a large series of MCT.

Methods: Clinical and dermoscopic images of histopathologically proven MCT intermingled with other tumors were randomly presented to clinicians with different levels of experience, blinded to the diagnosis and objective of the study. The clinical and dermoscopic diagnostic accuracies were measured separately. In the second part of the study, dermoscopic examination of 161 cases of MCT was performed.

Results: The study included 119 participants. The percentage of correct diagnoses was 8% by naked eye examination and 36.4% by dermoscopy ($P < 0.001$). The presence of the malignant component in the cases of MCT was not recognizable in 19.1% of cases by naked eye examination and in 11.8% of cases by dermoscopy ($P < 0.001$).

A total of 161 histopathologically proven cases of MCT were collected. The most frequent MCT was basal cell carcinoma-seborrheic keratosis collision tumor (CT) (37.9%), followed by basal cell carcinoma-melanocytic nevus CT (19.9%), and melanoma - seborrheic keratosis CT (6.8%). Diagnostic accuracy among experts on dermoscopy was 71.4%.

Discussion: The diagnosis of MCT can be assisted and clarified by dermoscopy. However, many of these lesions manifest complex morphologies and continue to be

challenging, even for experts on dermoscopy. Atypical, uncertain or non-classifiable lesions still need a complete excision for the final diagnosis.

Key words: Dermoscopy, collision tumors, basal cell carcinoma, melanoma, squamous cell carcinoma.

INTRODUCTION

The association of two or more different neoplasms in the same lesion is uncommon and has been reported as collision or compound tumors (CT) in the medical literature ^(1,2). Most of these CT are trivial and curiosities which are of no clinical relevance, for example in those cases composed of only benign tumors. However, this kind of tumors can be very relevant in the cases of the development of a malignant neoplasm in association with a benign lesion or when there is a co-existence of two malignant tumors ^(1,2). These benign-malignant (BMCT) or malignant-malignant collision tumors (MMCT) often manifest a strange morphology and pose diagnostic challenges. More importantly, BMCT are sometimes clinically recognizable for the benign portion because it is predominant in the lesion and therefore, they could be clinically misdiagnosed as benign, with all the consequences that would entail ^(3,4). Dermoscopy is a non-invasive *in vivo* technique which has greatly improved the diagnostic accuracy of pigmented and non-pigmented skin tumors compared to the naked eye evaluation ⁽⁵⁾. Clinical and dermoscopic features of malignant collision tumors (MCT) or CT with at least one malignant portion have been previously described only in case reports and small series ⁽³⁻⁶⁾. Little is currently known about the value of dermoscopy in the correct diagnosis of these tumors.

The primary goal of this study is to assess the accuracy of the diagnosis of CT comparing the naked eye and dermoscopic examination. Moreover, we consider it worthwhile

to communicate the dermoscopic features of the largest series of malignant collision tumors (MCT) published to date.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

First part of the study: Dermoscopic images of 161 histopathologically proven cases of MCT collected at 15 Hospitals in Spain, France, Turkey and Italy were evaluated. The lesions were obtained from the image archives of 15 experienced dermoscopists with at least 10 years of experience. Clinical data was obtained for each patient, including: age and gender of patients, the anatomical location of the lesions and the clinical diagnosis or differential diagnoses of the MCT before excision. Dermoscopic images of each lesion were obtained using DermLite Foto (3Gen, LLC, Dana Point, CA, U.S.A.) mounted on a digital camera at 20 to 50-fold magnification. No pressure was used to avoid the collapse of the vessels in the lesions.

Second part of the study: The experiment was a laptop-based image study of skin tumors. It was divided into two image sets. Each image set consisted of a PowerPoint slideshow of the same 30 skin lesions (first set with the clinical images and second set with the dermoscopic images). All the lesions were presented with brief information (the age and gender of the patient and location of the lesion). The 30 skin lesions of the sets were 13 MCT (6 basal cell carcinoma – melanocytic nevus CT, 4 basal cell carcinoma – seborrheic keratosis CT, 1 melanoma – seborrheic keratosis CT, 1 melanoma – basal cell carcinoma CT and 1 basal cell carcinoma – sebaceous hyperplasia CT) admixed with other 17 lesions (5 melanomas, 2 angiokeratomas, 2 basal cell carcinomas, 2 seborrheic keratoses, 1 dermatofibroma, 1 clear cell acanthoma, 1 Spitz nevus, 1 sebaceous hyperplasia, 1 cutaneous leishmaniasis and 1 tungiasis) with biopsy confirmation of the diagnoses. The 30 lesions used in each image set were drawn

at random from the collection of 161 MCT and the image archives of Hospital de Sant Pau I Santa Tecla. A second random draw determined the order in which the lesions appeared in the PowerPoint slideshow. Photographs were standardized for size and magnification.

The participants of the study were attending an advanced course of dermoscopy in Barcelona. They were dermatologists and dermatology residents with different levels of experience in dermoscopy. The participants were not aware of the study's aim or the inclusion criteria of the lesion images shown. The clinical image set was first presented to participants and later they had to evaluate the dermoscopic image set. They were asked to diagnose the cases and had 15 minutes to evaluate each set (30 seconds per slide).

Statistical analysis: Categorical variables were summarized in terms of percentages and 95% confidence interval, and for continuous variables mean and standard deviation (SD) were obtained. Differences between mean values were assessed by t-student test and differences between proportions were assessed by chi-squared test. A *P* value <0.05 was considered statically significant. All analyses were performed using IBM SPSS version 24 for windows, Chicago Ill. USA.

RESULTS:

First part of the study: A total of 161 histopathologically proven cases of MCT were included (Figure 1). The lesions were obtained from 94 men (58.4%) and 67 women (41.6%) ranging in age from 23 to 97 years (mean 67.3 ± 13.9 years). Of the 161 lesions, 79 were located on the trunk (49%), 71 on the head or neck (44%), and 11 on the extremities (7%). The most frequent CT was basal cell carcinoma (BCC)-seborrheic

keratosis (SK) CT (37.9%) (Figure 2), followed by BCC-melanocytic nevus (N) CT (19.9%) (Figure 3), and melanoma (MM) - SK CT (6.8%) (Figure 4). The most commonly detected malignancy in the MCT was BCC (n = 125), followed by MM (n = 19) and squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) (n = 13). BCC was associated more frequently with SK (n = 61), N (n = 32), angiomas (Ang) (n = 7), solar lentigines (SL) (n = 4), dermatofibromas (DF) (n = 3), SCC (n = 3) and MM (n = 3). MM was associated with SK (n = 11), BCC (n = 3), Ang (n = 3), SL (n = 1), actinic keratosis (AK) (n = 1), and SCC (n = 1). SCC was associated with SK (n = 7), BCC (n = 3), MM (n = 1), Ang (n = 1), and SL (n = 1). SK was the most common benign neoplasm (n = 84), followed by N (n = 34). The percentage of correct diagnoses among experts on dermoscopy was 71.4%.

Second part of the study: Second study included 119 participants. Their average age was 38.9 years (SD = 9.7) and 29.4% were men. No differences were found between age, gender and years of experience and ratio of correct diagnoses. The percentage of correct diagnoses was 8% (n = 124) with naked eye examination and 36.4% (n = 563) with dermoscopy (P <0.001) (Figure 5). The MCT with more wrong diagnoses by naked eye examination was BCC-sebaceous hyperplasia (SH) CT (99.2%), followed by BCC-MM CT (97.5%) and BCC-SK CT (97.3%). By dermoscopy, the percentage of wrong diagnoses for the case BCC-SH CT was 94.1%, 67.2% for BCC-MM and 64.9% for BCC-SK. The presence of the malignant component was not detected in 19.1% of MCT by naked eye examination and in 11.8% of cases by dermoscopy (P <0.001).

DISCUSSION

The presence of more than one tumor in the same lesion is rarely observed but well documented⁽¹⁻⁶⁾. The nomenclature of these neoplasms was previously confusing

as many terms (collision, combined, colonized and biphenotypic tumors) had been used interchangeably. However, this terminology was recently defined and clarified by Satter et al. ⁽²⁾: a) Collision tumors: defined as the merging of 2 originally separate, adjacent, and often well demarcated neoplasms within close proximity of each other; b) Combined tumors: a neoplasm consisting of at least two cell populations that are intimately admixed; c) Colonized tumors: defined as one tumor cell population permeating and colonizing an underlying second tumor cell population; d) Biphenotyping tumors: combined tumors consisting of at least two populations of tumor cells that arise from a common precursor and undergo subsequent divergent differentiation ⁽²⁾. CTs have been observed for benign-benign neoplasms (BBCT), benign-malignant neoplasms (BMCT) and malignant-malignant neoplasms (MMCT). According to our study of 161 MCT, the three most common combinations were BCC-SK (37.9%; 61 cases), BCC-N (19.9%; 32 cases) and MM-SK (6.8%; 11 cases). The BCC-SK CT was also the most frequent combination in the two dermoscopic series about collision tumors published in the literature: Moscarella et al ⁽⁴⁾ found the BCC-SK association in 29.2% of their 24 CT and Blum et al ⁽⁶⁾ observed the BCC-SK combination in 23.4% of their 77 CT. Boyd and Rapini ⁽¹⁾ performed a retrospective study of 40000 cutaneous biopsies, yielding 69 examples of CT and the two most common combinations of benign-malignant lesions were also BCC-N (14 cases) and BCC-SK (8 cases). Afterwards, Cascajo et al ⁽⁷⁾ performed a retrospective analysis of 85000 histological examinations, obtaining 54 examples of associations between SK and malignant neoplasms, of which 43 were BCC. The two most common combinations of MMCT in our study were BCC-MM (3.7%; 6 cases: 3 superficial spreading melanomas, 2 lentigo maligna melanomas and 1 lentigo maligna) and BCC-SCC (1.9%; 3 cases). The only kind of MMCT found by Moscarella et al ⁽⁴⁾ were two cases of BCC-

MM CT and later Blum et al ⁽⁶⁾ collected 3 cases of MM-BCC, one MM-SCC in situ and one BCC-keratoacanthoma.

According to our study, preoperative diagnosis of cutaneous MCT is extremely difficult and dermoscopy improves the recognition of this kind of tumors. The percentage of correct diagnoses made by the participants of the study was only 8% by naked eye examination and clearly increased with dermoscopic examination (36.4%; $P < 0.001$). Moreover, this percentage significantly raised (71.4%) among the experts on dermoscopy so, as suggested by medical literature, diagnostic accuracy is dependent upon the experience of the examiner ⁽⁵⁾. In 2005, Zaballos et al ⁽⁸⁾ published 5 cases of CT (2 BCC-SK, 2 BCC-N and one BCC-DF) which were all correctly diagnosed dermoscopically and none, clinically. Later, Zaballos et al ⁽³⁾ reported a series of 19 cases of BCC-SK CT; the diagnoses of which were only correct in 31.6% of cases without dermoscopy whereas 100%, using dermoscopy. Moscarella et al ⁽⁴⁾ reported 24 cases of CT and the dermoscopic diagnoses were correct in 58.3% of cases.

The most important aspect of the evaluation of CT is the detection of the potential malignancies inside the tumor and it is important to note that, in our study, the presence of the malignant component in the cases of MCT was not recognizable in 19.1% of cases by naked eye examination. Dermoscopy has demonstrated to increase sensitivity for skin cancer detection compared to naked eye examination ⁽⁵⁾. Rosendhal et al ⁽⁹⁾ reported that the diagnostic accuracy for malignant neoplasms measured as area under receiver operating characteristics curves was 0.89 with dermoscopy and 0.83 without it ($P < .001$). It is well known that the three most common cutaneous neoplasms are BCC, SCC and MM. The diagnostic accuracy of dermoscopy for BCC diagnosis has been reported to range from 95% to 99%, depending on BCC subtype ⁽¹⁰⁾. The

dermoscopic diagnostic accuracy for SCC has been reported to be 86.5%⁽⁹⁾. Many dermoscopic features associated with the spectrum of premalignant and malignant keratinizing tumors (AK, Bowen's disease, keratoacanthoma and SCC) have been reported⁽¹¹⁾. Ryu TH et al⁽¹²⁾ reported an overall odds ratio (OR) for correct diagnosis of BCC and SCC of 2.847 using dermoscopy compared to the naked eye ($P < 0.0049$). When it comes to individual diagnosis, OR for SCC was 2.483 ($P = 0.052$) and OR for BCC was 4.048 ($P = 0.017$)⁽¹²⁾. Regarding melanoma, three meta-analyses have demonstrated the superiority and usefulness of dermoscopy compared to the naked eye⁽¹³⁻¹⁵⁾. The most recent one included only prospective studies performed in a clinical setting and found that the diagnostic odds ratio for melanoma was 15.6 times higher for dermoscopy than naked eye examination⁽¹⁵⁾. However, the coexistence of two malignant neoplasms in the same tumor (MMCT) is extremely rare and it is very difficult to suspect clinically even with dermoscopy. In our study, we collected 10 cases of MMCT (5BCC-MM, 3 BCC-SCC, 1 BCC-MM-trichoblastoma and one SCC-MM) and only one case was correctly diagnosed by the experts on dermoscopy. However, all the cases were dermoscopically diagnosed as malignant neoplasms. Among the cases of MMCT, the association of BCC and MM seems to predominate also in the literature^(4, 16-18). Piérard et al⁽¹⁸⁾ found 11 BCC-MM CT in a series of 78000 primary cutaneous neoplasms. Moscarella et al⁽⁴⁾, in their series of 24 CT, reported 2 BCC-MM CT; only one was correctly diagnosed on dermoscopy.

The association of a benign tumor with a malignant neoplasm (BMCT) is of particular importance. BMCT are sometimes clinically recognizable for the benign portion because it is predominant in the lesion and therefore, they could be clinically misdiagnosed as benign, with all the consequences that would entail^(3,4,8). In our study, the presence of the malignant component in the cases of BMCT was not recognizable by the participants in

19.1% of cases by naked eye examination and in 11.8% of cases by dermoscopy ($P < 0.001$). Regarding the experts on dermoscopy, the diagnoses were wrong in 39 cases of BMCT, of which 84.6% were dermoscopically diagnosed as malignant. In 2005, Zaballos et al ⁽⁸⁾ reported 5 BMCT which were all correctly diagnosed dermoscopically and only one was diagnosed as malignant without dermoscopy. In 2012, Zaballos et al ⁽³⁾ published a series of 19 BCC-SK CT which were correctly diagnosed dermoscopically; 52.6% of these lesions were diagnosed without dermoscopy as a SK. However, in 2013, Moscarella et al ⁽⁴⁾ published 18 cases of BMCT, of which 9 were incorrectly diagnosed dermoscopically and, what is more important, 5 of them were dermoscopically diagnosed as a benign tumor. The misdiagnosis of a BMCT as a benign tumor can be explained by the anchoring bias ⁽⁶⁾. This occurs when the observer anchors their diagnosis on the benign features within a BMCT and stops searching for features suggestive of malignancy. A good rule to avoid this bias is to evaluate all four quadrants of a lesion and to ensure the absence of criteria of malignancy in any quadrant ⁽⁶⁾. The use of other diagnostic techniques in conjunction with dermoscopy can improve the diagnostic accuracy of BMCT. Moscarella et al ⁽⁴⁾ reported that reflectance confocal microscopy (RCM) revealed the malignant component in 19 out of 20 cases of MCT (vs 14 cases by dermoscopy) and the Cohen's kappa for RCM/histopathology diagnosis was 0.965, being 0.677 for dermoscopy/histopathology diagnosis.

The present study has several limitations. The first part of the study was conducted retrospectively and the histopathologic diagnosis of MCT was based on the official pathology diagnosis from the corresponding centre; a second pathologist did not confirm the diagnoses. In the second part of the study, we assessed diagnostic accuracy through the artificial scenario of an image-based study, which may not be representative of diagnoses made during live patient examinations ⁽¹⁹⁾. Finally, all the images were polarized

and we have to warn the reader that the presence of some dermoscopic signs depends on the technique used (polarized vs. non-polarized).

In conclusion, the diagnostic accuracy of CT by naked eye examination is very limited and the correct diagnosis of many of these lesions is very difficult. The diagnosis of CT can be assisted and clarified by dermoscopy, above all for experienced dermoscopists, revealing structures and patterns associated with malignant tumors invisible to the naked eye and facilitating an accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment. However, many of these lesions manifest complex morphologies and continue to be challenging, even for experts on dermoscopy. Moreover, dermoscopy can also lead to anchoring errors, resulting in the missed opportunity to biopsy or excise a MCT. RCM could be a new additional and helpful diagnostic tool for these CT. However, atypical, uncertain or non-classifiable lesions still need a complete excision for the final diagnosis.

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FIGURES:

Figure 1.- Type and number of MCT and number of correct diagnoses made by the experts on dermoscopy. Abbreviation: S: BCC: basal cell carcinoma, SK: seborrheic keratosis; N: melanocytic nevus; MM: malignant melanoma; SCC: squamous cell carcinoma; Ang: angiomas; SL: solar lentigines; D: dermatofibromas; AK: actinic keratosis; LM: Lentigo maligna; LMM: Lentigo maligna melanoma; Other CT A: Rare collision tumors correctly diagnosed by dermoscopy (BCC-Ang-SK, BCC-SH, BCC-N-Ang, BCC-AK, LMM-AK, LM-AK-SK, MM-SL, keratoacanthoma-N; one case each); Other CT B: Rare collision tumors incorrectly diagnosed by dermoscopy (BCC-fibrofolliculoma, BCC-hidrocystoma, BCC-lymphangioma, BCC-MM-trichoblastoma, LM-SH, porocarcinoma-SK, SCC-LS, SCC-MM, BCC-cyst; one case each).

Figure 2.- BCC-SK CT. A1.- Asymptomatic pigmented tumor located on the thorax of an 81-year-old man. A2.- In the dermoscopic view, we can see a BCC (arborizing telangiectasias, multiple blue-gray globules and large blue-gray ovoid nests) in the left part of the lesion and a SK (comedo-like openings and milia-like cysts) in the right part. Only 2.5% of participants made a clinically correct diagnosis whereas this percentage was 68.1% using dermoscopy. B1- Asymptomatic pigmented tumor located on the face of a 70-year-old man. B2.- Dermoscopically, we can observe a SK (comedo-like openings and milia-like cysts) located on the left and a BCC (arborizing telangiectasias, multiple blue-gray globules and large blue-gray ovoid nests) located on the right. Only 2.5% of participants made a clinically correct diagnosis whereas, dermoscopically, this percentage was 36.1%. Both cases were correctly diagnosed by the experts on dermoscopy. (DermLite Foto; 3Gen, LLC, Dana Point, CA, U.S.A. Original magnification x 10).

Figure 3.- BCC-N CT. A1.- Asymptomatic tumor located on the back of a 38-year-old woman. A2.- In the dermoscopic view, we can see a BCC (arborizing telangiectasias, multiple blue-gray globules, a large blue-gray ovoid nest and a spoke-wheel-like structure) in the left part of the lesion and a N (brown globules and comma vessels) in the right part. Only 8.4% of participants made a clinically correct diagnosis whereas, dermoscopically, this percentage was 46.2%. B1.- Asymptomatic pigmented tumor located on the back of an 84-year-old man. B2.- Dermoscopically, we can observe a N (light brown homogeneous areas with comma vessels) located on the left and a BCC (leaf-like structures and large blue-gray ovoid nests) located on the right. The percentage of correct diagnoses was 13% clinically and 16% dermoscopically. Both cases were correctly diagnosed by the experts on dermoscopy. (DermLite Foto; 3Gen, LLC, Dana Point, CA, U.S.A. Original magnification x 10).

Figure 4.- Other CT. A1.- Asymptomatic tumor located on the face of a 70-year-old man. A2.- In the dermoscopic view, we can see a SH (yellowish globules in the centre with a surrounding crown of vessels) in the left part of the lesion and a BCC (ulceration, arborizing telangiectasias and a large blue-gray ovoid nest) in the right part. B1.- Asymptomatic pigmented tumor located on the back of a 65-year-old man. B2.- Dermoscopically, we can observe an angioma (red lagoons) located on the left and a MM (atypical pigment network, negative pigment network, atypical globules and regression structures) located on the right. C1.- Asymptomatic pigmented tumor located on a shoulder of a 77-year-old woman. C2.- In the dermoscopic view, we can see a MM (blue-white veil, atypical globules and pseudopods) in the left part of the lesion and a SK (comedo-like openings, milia-like cysts and keratin) in the right part. D1.- Pigmented tumor located on the face of a 70-year-old man. D2.- Dermoscopically, we can observe a LMM (annular-granular pattern with

rhomboid structures and a dark blotch) located on the left and a pigmented BCC (a large blue-gray ovoid nest with leaf-like structures) located on the right. Only the case A was included in the second part of the study and only 0.8% of participants made a clinically correct diagnosis whereas, dermoscopically, this percentage was 6%. The dermoscopic diagnoses of the experts were correct in the first three cases; the fourth case was diagnosed as a LMM. (DermLite Foto; 3Gen, LLC, Dana Point, CA, U.S.A. Original magnification x 10).

Figure 5.- Comparison between percentages of right diagnoses made by naked eye examination Vs dermoscopic examination. Abbreviation: S: BCC: basal cell carcinoma, SK: seborrheic keratosis; N: melanocytic nevus; SH: sebaceous hyperplasia, MM: melanoma. P value obtained by chi-squared test.

